

Action Plan of the Hungarian Young Academy (HYA) within the Framework of CoARA

1. Introduction

The Hungarian Young Academy (HYA) is a multidisciplinary organization that represents early- to mid-career researchers across Hungary and operates in accordance with the public duties of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences. Established with the mission to support scientific excellence and innovation, HYA serves as a platform for fostering collaboration, advocating for improved policies of early career researchers, and addressing the challenges faced by the next generation of scientists. HYA is committed to promoting a research culture that values integrity, diversity, and inclusivity.

As an advocate for progressive research practices, HYA recognizes the importance of aligning with international initiatives such as the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) and has joined CoARA as a member in 2024. By adopting CoARA principles, HYA aims to lead by example in the Hungarian research landscape, ensuring that research assessments are fair, transparent, and reflective of the diverse contributions made by researchers. This action plan outlines HYA's strategic vision and initiatives to advance responsible research assessment practices, focusing on young scientists within Hungary, thereby contributing to the global effort for a systemic change in evaluating research and researchers.

2. Strategic Objectives

2.1 Promote Responsible Research Assessment

- Advocate for assessment criteria that values scientific excellence (quality) over metrics (quantity) and values the diversity of academic activities and contributions (e.g. education, mentoring), beyond traditional bibliometric indicators.

2.2 Improve Research Culture

- Support a research environment that values innovative scientific ideas, collaboration, interdisciplinary approaches, and societal impact. Increase awareness related to predatory journals and to help researchers identify reputable journals, publishers and resources.

2.3 Build Awareness

- Educate the research community on CoARA principles and best practices in research assessment.

2.4 Align National Policies

- Engage with Hungarian stakeholders to harmonize research evaluation frameworks with CoARA principles.

2.5 Foster Mutual Learning and Collaboration

- Actively participate in CoARA international and national working groups, forums and exchange best practices.
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3. Key Initiatives

3.1 Join the Hungarian National Chapter, establish a Working Group within the HYA

- Implemented: The HYA has joined the CoARA Hungarian National Chapter, regular meetings are attended by HYA members.
- Planned: To form a dedicated team within HYA to drive the CoARA agenda, including members from diverse disciplines.

3.2 Address Predatory Journals and Publishers

- Implemented: Development and promotion of guidelines in association with the Hungarian Academy of Sciences to help researchers identify reputable journals and publishers.
- Planned: To raise awareness among researchers about the risks of publishing in predatory journals, leveraging HYA's communication channels to disseminate educational resources. To record short videos to educate researchers and raise awareness via various communication channels including social media platforms. To partner with institutions to provide training on evaluating journal credibility.

3.3 Improve Grant Review Processes for Young Scientists

3.3.1 Transition from Inappropriate Metric Use

- Implemented: Discussions have been initiated within HYA and workshops have been organized on reducing reliance on journal impact factor, h-indices, and metrics emphasizing quantitative research assessment (e.g. scientometrics.org).
- Planned: Pilot evaluation schemes that avoid these metrics and emphasize research content quality and relevance. Collaborate with funding bodies to create grant opportunities that prioritize scientific value, potential, and innovation over traditional metrics, and ensure that reviewers are trained to evaluate young scientists' proposals equitably.

3.3.2 Enhance the Focus on Expert Peer Review and Qualitative Assessment Practices

- Implemented: Efforts have been made to highlight to funding bodies the need for expert peer review as a central element of evaluation in grants and academic career assessment.
- Planned: Conduct surveys to identify strengths and gaps in current evaluation processes to enhance consistent, fair, and transparent grant evaluation procedures. To engage with key stakeholders (Hungarian research institutions, national and regional funding bodies policy makers and industry representatives) about the need to reform current evaluation processes and metrics. To collaborate with Hungarian research institutions to trial and refine new evaluation criteria that align with CoARA principles. To organize training sessions for reviewers to ensure consistent, fair, and transparent assessment. To publish recommendations

on appropriate assessment practices in general, and, tailored to specific grants, projects or institutions, particularly focusing on early career scientists, ensuring alignment with CoARA principles. To create resources, such as toolkits and guidelines, to assist institutions and researchers in adopting CoARA-compliant practices.

3.3.3 Actions to Recognize the Diversity of Academic Contributions

- Implemented: HYA has made a series of efforts in acknowledging diverse academic outputs, such as organizing workshops and publications promoting interdisciplinary research, education and societal impact.
- Planned: To develop initiatives that expand evaluation metrics to include contributions e.g. mentoring, science communication, and community engagement.

3.4 Improve the Situation of Women Researchers

- Implemented: Gender disparities in research assessments and career developments have been highlighted in HYA-authored research reports, workshops and discussions. As a result, initiatives of HYA addressing career interruptions have been implemented in grants (e.g. Bolyai grant), in publication/citation metrics websites (mtmt.hu and tscientmetrics.org).
- Planned: To advocate for gender-sensitive evaluation criteria in grants and career assessment evaluations, whenever feasible. To promote mentorship programs for women researchers, and support further initiatives that address career interruptions due to caregiving responsibilities to female and male researchers. To monitor progress in the situation of women researchers through extensive surveys. To initiate specific reintegration grants for scientists returning from parental leave.

3.5 Raise Awareness and Provide Training

- Implemented: HYA's communication channels have been used to share information on CoARA actions and principles among members.
- Planned: Host seminars and create online modules to educate stakeholders about responsible research assessment.

3.6 Foster Engagement in CoARA Working Groups and Establish International Partnerships

- Implemented: HYA has joined CoARA TIER (Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research and EMCR (Early- and Mid-Career Researchers, Assessment and Working Culture) Working Groups
- Planned: To actively participate in several CoARA Working Groups, forums and exchange best practices. To establish partnerships with other CoARA members, young national academies to co-develop assessment strategies. Actively participate in international discussions on improving research assessment.

3.7 Communicate Progress and Share Data

- Implemented: HYA's communication channels have been used to share information on previous achievements.

- **Planned:** To publish annual reports showcasing achievements in reforming research assessment. To advocate for the FAIR principles in scientific data management. Transparent communication of progress on achievements in reforming research assessment.
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4. Implementation Plan

4.1 Timeline

- **Year 1:** Establish a working group within HYA and conduct baseline surveys of research assessment practices, targeting specific grants and assessments of early career researchers in Hungary. Actively participate in CoARA Working Groups, forums.
- **Year 2:** Launch pilot programs and host national workshops. Educate and engage with stakeholders about responsible research assessment. Conduct regular events to raise awareness about responsible research assessment and disseminate CoARA guidelines.
- **Year 3:** Evaluate achievements, publish and disseminate findings.

4.2 Monitoring and Evaluation

- Qualitative and quantitative metrics will be used to track progress, including participant feedback from events and the adoption rate of new practices by institutions.
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5. Expected Outcomes

- Increased awareness and acceptance of CoARA principles within the Hungarian research community.
 - Development of research assessment frameworks that prioritize quality, scientific excellence, quality over quantity and societal impact.
 - Greater opportunities for early-career researchers through reformed grant review processes that focus on innovation and potential.
 - Stronger alignment of Hungarian research policies with international best practices.
 - Improved researcher capacity to identify and avoid predatory journals, enhancing the integrity of published research.
 - Enhanced equity and support for women researchers, contributing to a more inclusive academic environment.
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The Hungarian Young Academy is dedicated to advancing responsible research assessment through active engagement with CoARA principles. By implementing this action plan, HYA aims to foster a fair, inclusive, and impactful research culture in Hungary and contribute to the global movement for improved research evaluation.